

**Brand Loyalty vs Brand Switching: A Study of Mobile Phone Preferences in
Young Pakistani Adults in South Punjab**

Ahmad Hassan Ishmal Akhtar, Muhammad Shahzaib, Muhammad bin Tajammal,

Muneeb Fazal

Institute of Business Management and Administrative Sciences

Department of Management and HRM

The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan

Index

Abstract.....	3
Introduction.....	3
Research Gap	5
Research Questions.....	5
Literature Review.....	5
Research Methodology	7
Target Population and Sampling.....	7
Method of Analysing Data	8
Results and Conclusion.....	8
Demographics of the Subjects	8
Measurement Model.....	11
Hypothesis Testing.....	12
Final hypothesis testing table	12
References.....	13

Abstract

This paper studies the mobile phone preferences in Pakistani Young Adults and what factors influence brand loyalty and brand switching among young Pakistani consumers. GenZ have unique characteristics in their behaviour from their older counterparts. In current era of AI and Internet smartphone has become an essential part of our life that connect us with the rest of the world as world has now become a global village. The smartphone industry is growing rapidly with new innovations and features every year or so. Pakistan as a developing country is filled with smartphones that are cheaper and has better features made possible by Chinese manufacturers. Young adults and Adults can now afford better smartphones at competitive prices. Data in this study was collected by the help of cross-sectional survey that include 70 smartphone users as subjects. Using Literature review we found that even though the purchase of a mobile phone is subjective there are some factors that influence the customers i.e. young adults, to switch brands.

Study Indicated that Infinix has most loyal customer base as compared to other smartphone users and Apple is the most popular brand, The studies shows that the things that influence consumer switching behaviour of smart phones includes product quality as the primary factor. The study further reveals that customer satisfaction has positive affect on customer switching brands. Moreover, switching cost also played an important role.

Keywords: Brand switching; Brand Loyalty; product quality; Product features; young adults; reference group; mobile phone and GenZ and switching costs.

Introduction

Mobile Phones today has become an important part of our life as they are becoming affordable and convenient therefore mobile advertising is also increasing according a report

showing advertisers spent \$6.43 billion globally on mobile ads (Leon Schiffman & Joe Wisenblit, p. 197) as smartphones.

Customer loyalty has become one of central figure that generate benefits and maintain their advantage to other corporations Consumer's loyalty has been reported to be declining. One report shows that consumers loyalty to products has decline to 30% in 2016 as against 44% in 2012 (Cooperative Credit Purchasing Company, 2017) It means customer switching behaviour has also been increasing overtime.

The present global smart phone market is estimated as 6.6 billion networks with global revenues of \$1.5 trillion last year (Statista, 2025; Ericsson, 2024). As smartphones are becoming smarter everyday customers expectations are increasing immensely, they now need new technologies in their daily life such as smart Bluetooth headphones, smart watches, fitness trackers, and connectivity of those accessories with their smartphone as it can match their lifestyle (Gartner, 2024).

As we talked about earlier mobile advertising could be a source for brand switching or brand loyalty it depends on what type of service the person is getting (Dwivedi et al., 2021). As GenZ today has totally different behaviour some are variety seeking some prefer simplistic designs, and some are influenced by social media influencers and seek luxury (Priporas et al., 2017; Djafarova & Bowes, 2021).

Pakistani Youngsters are of same mindset as brand loyalty is losing daily due to brand switching (Khan et al., 2021; Akram et al., 2022) as smartphones are not only for communication now, they have become a tool that everyone needs for entertainment, navigation or socializing with increasing exposure to new brand leads to switching (Dwivedi et al., 2021; GSMA, 2024).

Research Gap

Although many researches have examined brand loyalty, trust and other determinants in developed markets (e.g., Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Jones et al., 2002; Matzler et al., 2008) very few researches are conducted in underdeveloped countries. In addition, past studies have mainly focused on either loyalty or switching rather than directly comparing both constructs within a single hybrid framework. This creates a theoretical gap in understanding how loyalty and switching interact in shaping a consumer's final purchase behaviour. Moreover, mobile phone preferences are not studied in this area.

Research Questions

1. What factors influence young adults to brand switching behaviour?
2. Does brand loyalty and trust backed by customer satisfaction mediate the brand switching behaviour due to product quality peer pressure or switching price?

Literature Review

In today's world smart phones have become an integral part of our life, smartphones are becoming smarter day by day, they are getting cheaper and with modern features they attract a lot of customers one of the major customers are young people. As Pakistan is a developing country like many south Asian countries smartphone here also has become a symbol of progress.

Young people are more favourably go towards change (Modahl, 2000; Mulhern, 1997; Schiffman & Kanuk, 2008), today's generation is variety seeking, influenced by influencers and trendsetters for their buying decisions. As world is progressing functional and luxury needs are also increasing as people life style is enhancing. Young people use social media on mobile phones even now young ones too, they use that not only for communication but

entertainment and shopping too (Bordeau et al., 2002; Joines,

Scherer, & Scheufele, 2003). A study of the demographics and their impact on consumer smartphone buying behavior was conducted by Binge, Ruiz, and Sanz (2005). Young people spend their large amount of their lives with their mobile phones, apart from the educational or formal purposes. They are tech savvy and advanced and shop online either through laptop or mobile phones. That's the main reasons for the growth in consumer grade computers and mobile handhelds.

Several studies have focused on factors as causes of customer loyalty in different areas and tried to understand the relationships between the factors, such as quality of the service and brand trust. Most of studies have demonstrated those factors have positive correlation with customer loyalty (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Chinomona et al., 2013; El Manstrly et al., 2011; Lui et al., 2017; Matzler et al., 2008; Ngo & Pavelkova, 2017; Zhang & Mattila, 2015). However, fewer studies have tried to understand the relationships between switching costs and customer loyalty even though evidence shows switching costs will increase switching difficulty or prevent consumer switching behavior (Jones et al., 2002).

Customer Loyalty is defined as a commitment to repurchase using same brand even the situation influences you to switch the brands (Oliver, 1997). Brand Trust is also an important determinant of brand loyalty and its commitment to buy again from the same brand and it rely on the brands ability to perform the promised function (Chaudhuri & Holdbrook, 2001) and Switching costs are the perceived costs when customer moves one brand to another it could be psychological or monetary (Heide & Weiss, 1995).

Conceptual Model

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis	Relationship
H1	Product Quality (PQ) → Customer Satisfaction (CS)
H2	Product Quality (PQ) → Trust (T)
H3	Peer Pressure (PP) → Customer Satisfaction (CS)
H4	Peer Pressure (PP) → Trust (T)
H5	Price & Features (PF) → Brand Loyalty (BL)
H6	Brand Loyalty (BL) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)
H7	Customer Satisfaction (CS) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)
H8	Trust (T) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)

Research Methodology

Target Population and Sampling

The subjects consist of young adults and adults over the age of 27. The sample size of the current study is 70. The data used for the analysis was collected in May, 2026 from different districts of

South Punjab, Pakistan. Samples were collected using convenience sampling method.

The sample consists of various people of different backgrounds and education. The subjects were asked to fill the questioner online on onsite for data collection purposes.

Method of Analysing Data

Data analysis was performed in two stages. Descriptive statistics was calculated using IBM SPSS to outline the demographic profile of the subjects and Partial Least Structural Equation Modelling was executed via SmartPLS it followed structural model hypotheses via bootstrapping procedure to evaluate its reliability and validity.

Results and Conclusion

Demographics of the Participants

Age

Age	Frequency	(%)
15-18	6	8.7
19-22	45	65.2
23-26	13	18.8
27+	5	7.2
Total	69	100.0

Gender

Group	Frequency	(%)
Male	46	66.7
Female	22	31.9
Prefer not to Say	1	1.4
Total	69	100.0

Possession of Current Brand

Brand	Frequency	(%)
Apple	13	18.8
Samsung	11	15.9
Infinix	10	14.5
Vivo	11	15.9

Google	2	2.9
Oppo	3	4.3
Xiaomi	4	5.8
Tecno	7	10.1
Others	8	11.6
Total	69	100.0

Figure 2 Most Popular Brands among Participants

Brand Loyalty by Age

Loyalty Index			
Age	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
15-18	3.2222	6	1.55873
19-22	3.2667	45	1.26850
23-26	3.4359	13	1.07484
27+	2.8667	5	1.40633
Total	3.2657	69	1.24798

Figure 3 Loyalty among Age group in Participants

Loyalty

&

Switching by Brand

Current Brand		Loyalty Index	Switching Index
Apple	Mean	2.8462	3.2308
	Std. Deviation	1.06819	1.69085
Samsung	Mean	3.0606	2.8182
	Std. Deviation	1.26331	1.40130
Infinix	Mean	4.0000	3.2000
	Std. Deviation	.95581	1.13529
Vivo	Mean	3.4848	2.8182
	Std. Deviation	1.32802	1.66242
Google	Mean	3.6667	4.0000
	Std. Deviation	.94281	.00000
Oppo	Mean	3.2222	1.6667
	Std. Deviation	2.03670	1.15470
Xiaomi	Mean	3.0000	4.5000
	Std. Deviation	.98131	1.00000
Tecno	Mean	2.7143	3.4286
	Std. Deviation	1.36665	1.81265
Others	Mean	3.5417	3.0000
	Std. Deviation	1.46859	1.30931
Total	Mean	3.2657	3.1159
	Std. Deviation	1.24798	1.48062

Figure 4 Loyalty and Switching Behavior Trend Among Participants

Measurement Model

Latent Variable (Construct)	Survey Items	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (ρ_{α})	Composite reliability (ρ_{ϵ})	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Trust (T)	TR1, TR2, TR3	0.877	0.897	0.924	0.803
Product Quality (PQ)	PQ1, PQ2, PQ3	0.790	0.918	0.864	0.681
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	CS1, CS2, CS3	0.727	0.756	0.839	0.635
Peer Pressure (PP)	PP1, PP2, PP3	0.711	0.783	0.841	0.644
Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)	BSB1, BSB2, BSB3	0.684	0.867	0.806	0.599
Brand Loyalty (BL)	BL1, BL2, BL3, BL4	0.676	0.676	0.789	0.483
Price & Features (PF)	PF1, PF2, PF3	0.398	0.630	0.688	0.486

The measurement model evaluation approves acceptable internal consistency and convergent validity for the research framework (Hair et al., 2017).

Hypothesis Testing

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Original sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P values</i>
<i>Brand Loyalty (BL) -> Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)</i>	0.221	0.155	0.202	1.090	0.276
<i>Customer Satisfaction (CS) -> Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)</i>	-0.152	-0.076	0.316	0.481	0.630
<i>Peer Pressure (PP) -> Customer Satisfaction (CS)</i>	0.392	0.326	0.218	1.798	0.072
<i>Peer Pressure (PP) -> Trust (T)</i>	-0.069	-0.066	0.285	0.242	0.808
<i>Price & Features (PF) -> Brand Loyalty (BL)</i>	0.319	0.335	0.195	1.635	0.102
<i>Product Quality (PQ) -> Customer Satisfaction (CS)</i>	0.489	0.571	0.184	2.650	0.008
<i>Product Quality (PQ) -> Trust (T)</i>	0.623	0.597	0.272	2.291	0.022
<i>Trust (T) -> Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)</i>	0.129	0.105	0.349	0.369	0.712

To evaluate the structural model and test the hypotheses, a PLS-SEM bootstrapping procedure was performed with 5,000 subsamples, utilizing mean replacement to account for missing values.

Final hypothesis testing table

Hypothesis	Relationship	β Value	t-value	p-value	Decision
H1	Product Quality (PQ) → Customer Satisfaction (CS)	0.489	2.650	0.008	Accepted
H2	Product Quality (PQ) → Trust (T)	0.623	2.291	0.022	Accepted
H3	Peer Pressure (PP) → Customer Satisfaction (CS)	0.392	1.798	0.072	Rejected
H4	Peer Pressure (PP) → Trust (T)	-0.069	0.242	0.808	Rejected
H5	Price & Features (PF) → Brand Loyalty (BL)	0.319	1.635	0.102	Rejected

H6	Brand Loyalty (BL) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)	0.221	1.090	0.276	Rejected
H7	Customer Satisfaction (CS) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)	-0.152	0.481	0.630	Rejected
H8	Trust (T) → Brand Switching Behaviour (BSB)	0.129	0.369	0.712	Rejected

Hypotheses were accepted when the value of p became below 0.05 and was rejected when the p value exceeded 0.05.

p < 0.05

According to final Hypotheses testing we found that

1. Product Quality significantly influences Customer Satisfaction.
2. Product Quality significantly influences Trust.

This means subjects consider product quality an important factor that affect their satisfaction and trust toward a brand.

References

- Akram, U., Hui, P., Kaleem Khan, M., Tanveer, Y., & Mehmood, K. (2022). How website quality affects online impulse buying. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 34(2), 315–337.
- Cooperative Credit Purchasing Company. (2017). *Consumer loyalty trends report 2017*.
- Djafarova, E., & Bowes, T. (2021). ‘Instagram made me buy it’: Generation Z impulse purchases in fashion industry. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 59, 102345.
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Ismagilova, E., Hughes, D. L., Carlson, J., Filieri, R., Jacobson, J., Jain, V., Karjaluoto, H., Kefi, H., Krishen, A. S., Kumar, V., Rahman, M. M., Raman, R., & Wang, Y. (2021). Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and

- research propositions. *International Journal of Information Management*, 59, 102168.
- Ericsson. (2024). *Ericsson mobility report 2024*.
- Gartner. (2024). *Consumer technology trends and smart device connectivity report*.
- GSMA. (2024). *The mobile economy 2024*.
- Khan, M. A., Ahmed, R., & Iqbal, S. (2021). Brand switching behaviour among Pakistani smartphone users. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 7(2), 245–256.
- Priporas, C. V., Stylos, N., & Fotiadis, A. K. (2017). Generation Z consumers' expectations of interactions in smart retailing. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 77, 374–381.
- Schiffman, L. G., & Wisenblit, J. (2019). *Consumer behavior* (12th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Statista. (2025). *Global smartphone market revenue and users statistics*.